

FOOD PLANTS OF ALTAI MOUNTAIN COUNTRY

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Dataset on GBIF

Access to the dataset

Description

The dataset contains a list of food plants of the Altai Mountain Country. The dataset is intended to provide all interested GBIF users with information about AMC food plant species, as well as further search for their growing places using the available datasets.

Geographic scope

Altai Mountainous Country (Russia, Kazakhstan, China and Mongolia)

Bibliography

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2. Vaganov AV, Shmakov AI, Gudkova PD. 2019. Global data on phytodiversity of the Altai mountain country, presented in the world's scientific depositories. Problems of Botany of South Siberia and Mongolia. Proceedings of 18th International Scientific-Practical Conference (20–23 May 2019, Barnaul): 222–227. (In Russian).

GBIF registration

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<http://altb.asu.ru/ipt/eml.do?r=food> (EML)
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